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Socio-Cultural Factors Associated with Menstrual Waste Practices among Female Adolescents

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Abstract

This study examined the socio-cultural factors associated with menstrual waste management practice among female students in Rivers State College of Health Science and Management Technology. Four research questions guided the study. The descriptive survey design was adopted. The population of the study consisted of 770 female students residing in the college. The simple random sampling technique was used to select a sample size of 100 students. A standardized questionnaire with a reliability coefficient of 0.70 was used. Data analysis was done with the aid of the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) version 23.0 and descriptive statistical tools such as percentage and frequency count. The result shows that 15(19%) of the students agreed that lack of money forced them to use a piece of wrapper as tissue paper to manage their menses while 65(8%) disagreed. 60(75%) of the students agreed that they used tissue paper during your menses while 20(25%) disagreed. Further findings showed that 70(88%) of the students bag menstrual waste material in polythene bags after use, while 10(12%) did not. Also, 79(98.75%) of the students thought that improper disposal of waste material can be unsightly to neighbours within the immediate environment, while 1(1.25%) did not think so. It was concluded that the students displayed a good attitude towards the management and disposal of menstrual waste. It was recommended that government should recognize and include menstrual waste management in the national sanitation policy and action plan to beam the limelight on the issue and create opportunity for national conversation and correction action on the issue.

Keywords: socio-cultural factors, menstrual waste, menstruation, adolescent girls, waste, disposal.